

Developing Position Profile for Insurance Broker in Indonesia

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

In an industry that is engaged in the sale of services, human resources who carry out these service activities are a determining factor for company performance. Therefore, human resources that meet the qualifications are needed in order to meet the specified targets and maintain consistency of service quality. This phenomenon is clearly seen in the Insurance Brokerage industry, where in 2016 the Indonesian government introduced a regulation that regulates the minimum qualification requirements for Insurance Brokers to operate. The purpose of this research is to create a position profile to help set standards when recruiting and selecting insurance brokers. In forming a position profile using the theory of recruitment and selection of workforce based on competence according to Dubois et al (2004). This research is a qualitative research using case study method. The data collection technique used is the result of interviews supported by secondary data both provided by the company and documents outside the relevant company internal data. Interview participants from this study were the company's President Director, Human Resources Manager, and recruitment and selection staff. The results of the research conducted are to form a position profile of the Insurance Broker position which is used as the basis for recruitment and selection. The recommendation given is to implement a position profile that has been made as a standard in the recruitment and selection process for Insurance Brokers, and the procedure for making this position profile can be used to standardize other positions, and recommendations for future research provide a tool to identify the criteria in the position profile when conducting interviews.

Keywords: POSITION PROFILE, RECRUITMENT, SELECTION

Introduction

Human resources are one of the most important elements that must be owned by a company. Because without human resources it is almost impossible to carry out the company's business processes. Companies are competing to get quality workers who can meet the predetermined targets and are even expected to be able to contribute to developing the company into a leading company in its industry. So, to get and build human resources in accordance with the needs, it is also necessary to have good human resource management. One of the functions that can ensure companies get the workforce they want is staffing which is a process when the organization ensures that the number of workers with abilities matches the existing positions, staffing itself

involves job analysis, HR planning, recruitment, and selection activities. Previous studies have also tried to understand the function of staffing, especially in planning, recruitment, and selection activities. Human resource design has been shown to have a direct effect on the performance and performance of the company and the achievement of company goals (Azmy, 2018; Wildan, et al, 2020). Human resource design can also have an influence on the marketing carried out by the company, how the human resource planning can shape the image of the company (Nasution, 2019; Padmoyani and Rahmawati, 2018; Esch and Mente, 2018) from this marketing field will also greatly help increase candidates who are interested in applying to companies, because one of the problems that are often faced in recruitment activities is how companies can attract workers who have the desired abilities to apply in their companies (Shenoy and Aithal, 2018).

Designing a good recruitment system is one thing that has become an important factor in today's business world, but designing a targeted recruitment system is another thing. To be able to extract maximum performance from a workforce, candidates that match what is needed from the position or position needed (Bellionardi and Pujiarti, 2013; Sengul, 2017), because it is proven by research which states that companies do not get maximum performance of its employees because they do not have the qualified abilities for the position they occupy (Bellionardi and Pujiarti, 2013). By basing human resource management on the competence of the company, you will get benefits in the form of increased performance because the workforce has the ability and behavior that maximizes potential (Selfiana, 2019; Xiaoli and Zhangli, 2020; Karimi, et all, 2019; Palmer, et all, 2015). Not only improving performance, using competence as the basis for human resource planning will also help in terms of retaining employees to keep working at the company (Singh and Pathak, 2018).

This study will examine companies engaged in insurance brokerage/brokerage services and claims consultants. Since the issuance of new regulations from Indonesian Government, it is stated that every insurance broker who wants to be declared official must go through education carried out by APARI (Association of Insurance Brokers of the Republic of Indonesia) and have a BNSP certification according to the position. The company has difficulties in finding candidates who have the abilities that meet the existing requirements, and have personality values that are in line with the values of the company. Therefore, the researcher will discuss the formation of a recruitment strategy that conforms to the regulations issued by the government regarding Business Licensing and Institutional Insurance Brokerage Companies, Reinsurance Brokerage Companies, and Insurance Loss Assessing Companies at company A.

From the results of interviews conducted, there is also a statement that there is a problem in recruitment where companies are faced with the choice of looking for candidates who have met the requirements of the regulations but have a tendency to be not fluent in technology, on the one hand when choosing to try to find potential candidates who will be built from scratch. given education and financed with certification, indeed the risk for the candidate who is not fluent in technology will not be a problem but the risks faced are greater, among which candidates who have been financed have the possibility of quitting or failing from APARI education and another possible risk is that the candidate is taken by other insurance brokerage firms. Therefore, the company has obstacles to create a recruitment strategy that can ensure getting workers who meet the regulations introduced

by the government.

Research question

After conducting interviews and discussions with the company, and based on the problems in the background of the problems and problems faced by the company, two research questions were formulated, including:

1. Why company A have difficulty in getting adequate human resources?
2. What is the position profile that can ensure company A get the required insurance broker in accordance with government regulations and company criteria?

Literature review

Insurance Broker

Based on the Financial Services Authority Regulation No. 70 of 2016, Insurance Broker is defined as a person who works for an Insurance Broker company and fulfils the requirements to provide recommendations or represent policyholders, the insured, or participants in conducting insurance coverage and/or settlement of claims. This definition is also stated in the Law of the Republic of Indonesia No. 40 of 2014 concerning insurance.

Competency-based human resource management

Competency-based human resource management looks at the needs of the results and job roles of the organization or requirements that are more individual-oriented than the job-oriented perspective. This approach makes competency the foundation of the overall function of human resource management. Recruitment is the process of attracting as many qualified applicants as possible for a vacancy. Recruitment is a talent search, the pursuit of the best group of applicants for an available position. Selection is the process of reducing the number of applicants to those who are truly qualified to achieve the desired results.

Competency based recruitment and selection

Competency-based recruitment begins when organizational leaders identify key work roles, positions, or work placements that require recruitment effort. This process involves setting priorities. The decision maker must also determine the length of time the recruitment will take place.

Information obtained from job analysis which is a component of the Position profile must meet the following requirements:

- Work results, activities and assignments as well as job competencies and behavioural indicators that competencies can be measured clearly and in harmony, and which managers seeking job applicants agree on;
- Competencies required for successful job performance;

- Key competencies that are the biggest predictor of job success are identified and validated by managers who need job applicants.

Research method

The type of research used in this study is a qualitative research. The research method used in this research is a case study research method. This study uses two sources of data, namely primary data from interviews conducted with company leaders and secondary data from relevant documents.

This research model used it:

Result and discussion

Based on the results of interviews with resource persons, the first problem faced was the emergence of government regulation which determined the minimum certification/qualifications that must be possessed by those who are engaged in the insurance brokerage business. This regulation makes those who do not meet the qualifications unable to operate as insurance brokers, in dealing with this problem the company has two ways to overcome it. Among other things: firstly, they recruit individuals who have met the minimum qualifications issued by the government, and the second way is to run an insurance broker education program which is intended for fresh graduates who have the interest and talent to become insurance brokers, this scholarship program is an activity which must be done by insurance brokerage companies where this is also a demand from the association and has its own budget allocation. These two methods were carried out after they tried to encourage and motivate employees in the company to continue their studies in order to achieve minimum qualifications but experienced rejection.

When recruiting those who already have qualifications, they tend to be old and difficult to develop, in addition, because they already have qualifications and previous work experience, the incentives offered often exceed the expectations and budget that have been determined, another problem found is because insurance brokers are positions that vulnerable to taking actions that can harm the company, an in-depth background check of applicants is needed to see what was the reason for them to leave the previous company and how their attitudes and behavior within the company were, whether they left because of behavioral problems or even committing fraud, which can be detrimental to the company's performance.

A voting system that is carried out when there are two or more candidates who have passed the interview stage

with the CEO. The voting system is carried out by those involved in conducting interviews, starting from HRD, Head of Section, GM, Board of Directors, and Board of Directors. The problem in this system is that voting is carried out based on individual preferences, indeed these preferences are based on the knowledge and experience they have, but there is a habit factor if the candidate has a certain status, for example having a relationship with the interviewer, and in the absence of standardization in the form of a document. which can be used as a benchmark for consideration in selecting which candidate to be offered a job offer. From that need, there are two ways to fulfil it, recruiting and selecting individuals who apply and meet the qualification standards, the second comes from the insurance broker education scholarship program. However, in conducting recruitment and selection for the position of insurance broker itself, it does not yet have a detailed job profile. In the absence of the job profile, there is no benchmark for standardization and in the end, it is very dependent on the preferences and ability to identify/profile the interviewee. According to the interviewees, the dependence on the preferences and abilities of the interviewees had led to an incident where the recruited broker had a bad influence because the values and culture he held were not in accordance with the values and culture built within the company.

For this reason, in trying to overcome this problem, I propose to create an insurance broker job profile with content that includes not only technical competence but also followed by the attitude criteria and desired values of an insurance broker.

Position profile

In making a position profile that will be used as the basis for the recruitment and selection process. The components in the making of this model are based on the requirements in the government regulation on Business Licensing and Institutional Insurance Brokerage Companies, apart from regulations issued by the state these components are also based on the results of discussions with the parties concerned from company.

Position:	Insurance Broker
Definition:	Individuals who work for Insurance Brokerage companies and meet the requirements to provide recommendations or represent policyholders, insureds, or participants in conducting insurance coverage and/or settlement of claims.
Responsibility:	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Providing services in insurance brokerage 2. Develop and expand services to clients 3. Handling current policies and renewal policies 4. Implement changes to the insurance broker's client insurance program.
Work Expectations:	Meet the monthly and annual targets set by the company.
Minimum work experience:	3 years in the field of insurance and have
Minimum Education:	High School/Equivalent.

Expertise Certification:	Have a Level 5 Broker V Certificate, and AAPAI/APAI/CIIB/Equivalent Insurance Profession Certificate.
Ability indicators:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Negotiation, • Analytical Thinking • Information Seeking • Problem Solving • Communication
Behavioral Indicators:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communicative, • Self-confident, • Target oriented, • Team workers, • Have a desire to learn, • Integrity, • Innovative.
Additional Terms:	Registered as a member of the Association of Insurance Brokers of the Republic of Indonesia (APARI)

Conclusion

After conducting interviews, discussions, and analysis of the recruitment and selection problems faced by the company, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. The emergence of government regulations in 2016, which stipulates minimum requirements, especially in certification which makes many brokers who work in companies not comply with these rules. However, with the current recruitment and selection system, the results are often inconsistent because it really depends on the preferences and abilities of those conducting the interview to dig up the information, they want to get from job applicants. This inconsistency in recruitment and selection is also due to the fact that the company does not have a standard that is used as a document that can be used as a basis for selecting job applicants.
2. In ensuring company A to get the insurance broker needed in accordance with the regulations and criteria from the company is to form a position profile that is in accordance with the points that must be owned by the existing position profile theory of human resource management based on competence (Dubois, et al 2004), position profile This is used as the basis for conducting the recruitment and selection process.

Recommendation

Based on the conclusions drawn, the following are recommendations that can be given:

1. It is advisable to implement the position profile that has been created to be used in conducting recruitment and selection. By implementing a position profile, it will provide clarity for what competencies an insurance broker must possess which will help provide standards during the recruitment and selection process. The procedure for making this position profile can be used to standardize other positions.

2. Suggestions for further researchers is to identify the competencies that make up the position profile, not only by interviewing but also by means of Focus Group Discussions by gathering those who have positions that they want to study and discussing what competencies are needed in the position. It should also be noted that certain positions have standards regulated by the government or already have certain competency standards that can indeed be used as a basis for identifying the competencies required for the position. It is also advisable for future research to include instruments that can be used to help identify the criteria that have been determined in the position profile when conducting interviews.

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